

SPORT BASED ACTUAL COACHING BEHAVIOUR OF COACHES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

Coach's leadership behaviour is a complex and diversified behaviour; it guides player to reach the goal through direct or indirect ways. An outstanding coach should possess training basics and abilities to enhance player's body and mind, and also make much of using skills, strategy, and process to encourage player to work voluntarily toward his goal. The purpose of the research study was to investigate the coaches' perspective about actual coaching behaviour based on their' sports. An independent sample T test is often used to compare the mean scores of variables for two different groups of participants. The results shows there were no significant difference exist in coaches' actual coaching behaviour based on their sport in the following variables such as democratic behaviour, autocratic behaviour, training and instruction as the p value in these cases are all greater than 0.05.

Key Words: Actual Leader Behaviour, Individual & Team Sport

Introduction

This is a topic that has been researched considerably, both inside and outside of the athletic context. According to Northouse (2003), goal attainment is one of the four components of leadership. He contends that much of the leader's focus should be on facilitating the movement to the goals of the organization. Therefore, the importance of quality leadership cannot be underestimated. Leadership research began to expound in the second half of the 20th century. Models of leadership were developed and tested. Outside of sport, there has been research on the generational differences between today's generation and those 30-40 years ago. Yu and Miller (2005) agree that leaders must be able to adapt to multiple types of workers. The premise in these empirical studies suggests that appropriate leadership for older generations might be misguided for today's subordinates. Therefore, it seems reasonable to assume the preferred and actual leadership of athletes and coaches has also changed with the generations. With the findings of this study, widely accepted sport leadership practices may be tested and, if appropriate, adjusted to better fit with the athletes from the current generation. There has been conflicting research about the significance of coaches' characteristics and perspectives of leadership. The present study will give further insight into the model to in fact, determine differences if any, between coaches actual coaching behaviours based on their sport. There is a practical significance to the present study. According to existing theories, if the preferred behaviour matches the actual behaviour, member satisfaction increases (Chelladurai, 1980). Therefore, if coaches understand the coaching behaviour they are giving and their teams prefer, they could adapt their coaching behaviours in order to increase their athletes' satisfaction and possibly, performance.

Research Questions: Do any differences exist between coaches' actual coaching behaviour based on their sport?

Research Hypothesis: There may have significant difference in actual coaching behaviour reported by coaches based on their sport.

Materials & Methods: Researchers method was of survey type that data were gathered emphasizing on field method and applying questionnaire.

The questionnaire data will be gathered from 64 coaches of individual and team sport were selected from state sports hostels in Kerala state. The coaches' age ranges from 35-55 years Participation in the study is voluntary and confidential; this was stated explicitly in the one- page covering letter attached to the questionnaire. Questionnaires were delivered to the respondents by the organizations' internal mail. All of the respondents completed the same version of the questionnaire and returned it in a sealed and prepaid envelope directly to the researcher.

- ✓ Coaches self evaluation version of the Revised Leadership Scale for Sport (RLSS) were utilized in the present study. (Zhang and Jensen, 1997). The RLSS has a total of 60 items, measuring six subscales of coaching behaviour such as positive feedback, democratic behaviour, autocratic behaviour, social support, situational consideration and training and instruction.

Research Design: The analysis has done based on the six dimensions of sport leadership outlined in the RLSS. An independent t-test was carried out to check the difference between sport based actual coaching behaviour reported by coaches'. Data was analyzed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20.0.

Analysis of Results Relating to Actual Coaching Behaviour: The table-I depicts the mean, std deviation, t value in all the subscales of actual version of coaching behaviour.

Comparative Independent ‘t’ Test and Descriptive Analysis on Subscales of Actual Coaching Behaviour between Individual and Team Sports:

Group Statistics						
Playing Sport		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t
Positive Feedback	Individual	64	51.05	5.458	.682	4.31*
	Team	64	54.59	3.676	.460	
Democratic Behaviour	Individual	64	43.81	6.554	.819	.967
	Team	64	42.55	8.165	1.021	
Autocratic Behaviour	Individual	64	26.69	5.092	.637	1.21
	Team	64	25.70	4.085	.511	
Social Support	Individual	64	31.81	3.775	.472	2.26*
	Team	64	30.44	3.091	.386	
Situational Consideration	Individual	64	42.45	5.046	.631	2.15*
	Team	64	44.00	2.755	.344	
Training & Instruction	Individual	64	41.88	5.650	.706	1.24
	Team	64	42.88	3.104	.388	

Description:

From table 1, it shows that the mean value of Positive feedback between individual and team sport are 51.05 and 54.69 respectively. The obtained ‘t’ -value is 4.31 which was greater than the tabulated t-value 1.98. Hence there was significant difference between the Positive feedback between individual and team sport on actual coaching behaviour. The mean value of Democratic Behaviour between individual and team sport are 43.81 and 42.55 respectively. The obtained ‘t’ -value is .967 which was lesser than the tabulated t-value 1.98. Hence there was no significant difference between the Democratic Behaviour between individual and team sport on actual coaching behaviour. The mean value of Autocratic Behaviour between individual and team sport are 26.69 and 25.70 respectively. The obtained ‘t’ -value is 1.21 which was lesser than the tabulated t-value 1.98. Hence there was no significant difference between the Autocratic Behaviour between individual and team sport on actual coaching behaviour. The mean value of Social Support between individual and team sport are 31.81 and 30.44 respectively. The obtained ‘t’ -value is 2.26 which was greater than the tabulated t-value 1.98. Hence there was significant difference between the Social Support between individual and team sport on actual coaching behaviour. The mean value of Situational Consideration between individual and team sport are 42.45 and 44.00 respectively. The obtained ‘t’ -value is 2.15, which was greater than the tabulated t-value 1.98. Hence there was significant difference between the Situational Consideration between individual and team sport on actual coaching behaviour. The mean value of Training & Instruction between individual and team sport are 41.88 and 42.88 respectively. The obtained ‘t’ -value is 1.24, which was lesser than the tabulated t-value 1.98. Hence there was no significant difference between the Training & Instruction between individual and team sport on actual coaching behaviour.

Conclusion and Recommendation:

The results shows there were no significant difference exists in coaches’ actual coaching behaviour based on their sport in the following variables such as democratic behaviour, autocratic behaviour, training and instruction. This study gives many contradictory and supporting results with some previous researches. The results show variances in some subscales of actual coaching behaviour exhibited by coaches based on their sport.

Diagrammatical Representation of Actual Coaching Behaviour on Sports:

Mean Values of PF (Positive Feedback), DB (Democratic Behavior), AB (Autocratic Behavior), SS (Social Support), SC (Situational Consideration) and TI (Training & Instruction) between Individual and Team athletes'

References:

1. Altahayneh, Z. (2003). The effects of coaches' behaviors and burnout on the satisfaction and burnout of athletes. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. Florida State University, Tallahassee.
2. Andrew, D. (2004). The effect of congruence of leadership behavior on motivation, commitment, and satisfaction of college tennis players. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Florida State University, Tallahassee.
3. Anshel, M. H. (2003). Sport Psychology: From theory to practice (4th Ed.) San Francisco: Benjamin Cummings.
4. Arsenault, P. M. (2004). Validating generational differences: A legitimate diversity and leadership issue. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 24, 124-141.
5. Barnes, K. A. (2003). NCAA division I athletes' coaching behavior preferences. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. University of North Texas, Denton.
6. Bass, B. M. (1990). Bass and Stogdill's handbook of leadership: A survey of theory and research. New York: Free Press.
7. Beam, J. W., Serwatka, T. S., & Wilson, W. J. (2004). Preferred leadership of NCAA division I and division II intercollegiate student-athletes. *Journal of Sport Behavior*, 27(1), 3-17.
8. Birnbaum, M. H. (2004). Human research and data collection via the internet. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 55, 803-832.